

Cybersecurity Vulnerabilities and the Safeguarding of the Online Environment in University Libraries in Rivers State

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Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of the study was to examine cybersecurity vulnerabilities and the safeguarding of the online environment in University Libraries in Rivers State.

Methodology: A correlational research design was employed in the study. The study population comprised all 42 librarians and 9 system analysts from six university libraries in Rivers State. Census sampling was used to select all 41 librarians and 8 system analysts as the study sample. A structured questionnaire titled "Cybersecurity Vulnerability and Library Online Environment Questionnaire" (CVLOE) was used for data collection. It was a four-point rating scale questionnaire. Data was analysed using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC). The "r" coefficient of the PPMC was used to answer the research questions, while the p-value was used to test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

Findings: Based on the findings. There is a strong and significant relationship between network security, system security, application security and the safeguarding of online environments in university libraries in Rivers State. When the three security components work together, university libraries can safeguard their online environment. Poor infrastructure, limited technical skills, and a lack of necessary training are all challenges.

Conclusion: The study concludes that cybersecurity is a critical determinant in safeguarding the online environment of university libraries. Based on the findings, it was recommended that university libraries implement strong authentication, encrypted databases, and regular updates to strengthen network, system, and application security against cyberattacks. University libraries should provide regular training to enhance librarians' knowledge and skills in cybersecurity management and to upgrade their infrastructure to ensure a safe digital environment.

Keywords: Cybersecurity, Online environment, Safeguarding, University libraries

Introduction

We are in an era of digital transformation, in which even developing nations are gradually adopting interconnected network societies. This shift has led to increased digitisation across nearly all areas of social life, including health, education, commerce, and transportation, which now heavily depend on online platforms to function effectively. Libraries are also evolving, increasingly employing digital technologies to deliver information resources that support teaching, learning, and research. Moving from traditional print services to digital systems—such as electronic databases, repositories, automated

management software, and networked information services—has broadened access to knowledge. However, this also introduces new security risks. As library operations become increasingly intertwined electronically, the risk of cyberattacks—such as data breaches, unauthorised access, phishing, ransomware, and system manipulation—increases sharply. These threats can lead to the loss of sensitive user data, disrupt vital library services, and threaten the integrity and trustworthiness of academic resources (Odewale, 2017; Abdul et al., 2025).

Njoku (2023) highlights that cybersecurity vulnerabilities in university library online systems often stem from weak network setups, outdated software, poor data security practices, and low security awareness among staff and users. Because libraries handle vast amounts of sensitive data—such as user profiles, borrowing history, and institutional files—they become prime targets for cybercriminals. Furthermore, the integration of various digital platforms, including online catalogues and remote authentication systems, introduces multiple vulnerabilities that need comprehensive security measures.

Protecting university library online systems has become a vital institutional goal. Achieving effective cybersecurity involves combining strong technological safeguards, rigorous administrative policies, and ongoing user training. Measures like encryption, secure login processes, regular system updates, data backup protocols, and cybersecurity education can greatly minimise risks and boost system resilience. As libraries adopt more innovative technologies, enhancing their digital defences is crucial not only for safeguarding information resources but also for ensuring seamless academic services and maintaining user trust. This study, therefore, focused on identifying cybersecurity vulnerabilities and strategies to protect university library online systems.

Statement of the Problem

University libraries are increasingly relying on online systems for essential academic services and routine maintenance. These systems are becoming more vulnerable to cybersecurity threats. Despite the vital role libraries serve in managing digital resources, user data, and institutional knowledge, many university online library environments remain insufficiently protected. Cyberattacks such as unauthorised access, malware infections, data breaches, and system disruptions continue to increase, exposing vulnerabilities in networks, databases, and electronic service platforms. Such vulnerabilities threaten the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information and endanger the continuity of teaching, learning, and research activities that depend on these systems. Addressing these threats and ensuring proper protection of the online library environment requires this investigation.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between network security and the safeguarding of the university library's online environment?
2. What is the relationship between system security and the safeguarding of the university library's online environment?
3. What is the relationship between application security and the safeguarding of the university library's online environment?

Hypotheses

There is no significant relationship between network security and the safeguarding of the university library's online environment

1. There is no significant relationship between system security and the safeguarding of the university library's online environment
2. There is no significant relationship between application security and the safeguarding of the university library's online environment.

Literature Review

Sequel to the digital transformation of academic libraries, the shift toward an online environment that enables the smooth functioning of institutional repositories, e-resources, remote access, and integrated library management systems has made cybersecurity a central concern. As libraries expand their digital footprint, the need for robust security frameworks increases significantly to protect resources and user data and to ensure uninterrupted service. Three interlinked but distinct dimensions of security, such as network security, system security, and application security, have been prominently identified as foundational to protecting library online environments (Omotunde & Ahmed, 2023; Obim & Akpokurerie, 2023)

Network security is broadly defined as the set of policies, technologies, and practices designed to protect network infrastructure and data transmissions from unauthorised access, misuse, malicious attacks, or service disruption. As the gateway through which users, whether on campus or remote, access library services, a secure network serves as the first line of defence against external threats, including intrusion attempts, malware infiltration, data interception, and denial-of-service attacks. In essence, network security safeguards the confidentiality, integrity, and availability (CIA) of data in transit or communication across the library's digital environment.

Igbinovia and Ishola (2023) hold that network security is a critical aspect of securing library online systems. Digital libraries and academic networks require robust defences to prevent unauthorised access, intrusions, and data interception. Network security directly affects the availability, integrity, and resilience of library online systems. If the network is insecure, users may face service disruptions, data breaches, or unauthorised intrusions. Kont (2024) provides concrete evidence on how network security measures should be implemented, including the installation of firewalls, wireless security products, separation of public and staff LANs, secure server placement, intrusion detection, and regular backups, which have been identified as key network and server security practices. Akor et al. (2024) affirmed that measures help mitigate risks posed by unauthorised network access and external cyber threats, thereby preserving the integrity of digital library services.

Moreover, the evolving nature of cyber threats, particularly in environments with multiple remote access points and diverse user populations, such as libraries, calls for adaptive network security approaches rather than static defences. According to Farid et al. (2022), adaptive security models that employ continuous monitoring, real-time anomaly detection, and dynamic policy enforcement are vital in environments such as educational institutions, where network traffic patterns and user behaviours are variable. In university libraries, network security is indispensable for ensuring that library systems remain protected against external threats, cyberattacks, unauthorised access, and service interruptions, thereby supporting reliable access to digital information resources, user privacy, and sustainable operations. While network security protects external interfaces and data traffic, system security encompasses the protection of the internal computing infrastructure: operating systems, servers, hardware, server configurations, system-level access controls, patch management, system-environment hardening, and proper maintenance protocols.

Abubakar and Sani (2021) state that system security aims to ensure that the software and hardware that underpin library services are resilient against vulnerabilities, intrusions, exploitation, and internal failures, thereby preserving service delivery and data integrity at the core (Gujar & Pandey, 2024). In an academic library, servers may host online public access catalogues, institutional repositories, library management systems, and other databases. System security ensures that these backend infrastructures are protected against attacks, unauthorised modifications, and malware. Adenike and Raliat (2023) posit that system security is critical to ensuring that backend systems remain protected, resilient, and capable of delivering uninterrupted, secure services to users.

Application security, as noted by Oladokun et al. (2024), refers to the security measures embedded within software applications, including coding standards, authentication and authorisation mechanisms, secure configuration, input validation, data encryption, session management, and protection against common web vulnerabilities. John et al. (2025) argue that as libraries adopt web-based library management systems, online catalogues, digital repositories, remote user portals, and cloud-based services, the security of these applications becomes central to protecting user data, resource integrity, and overall system trustworthiness. Academic libraries, as noted by Jun (2023), should adopt robust applications to ensure the integrity of digital collections and to support secure remote access and service continuity (Aregbesola & Nwaolise, 2023).

Methodology

This study adopted a correlational research design. This is a research design that determines whether and to what extent a relationship exists between two or more variables, typically the study's independent and dependent variables. The university libraries considered in this research are Rivers State University Library, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Library, University of Port Harcourt Library, Pamo University of Medical Science Library and Madonna University Library. The population of the study will consist of all forty-one (41) librarians and eight (8) system analysts who are domiciled in the six universities' libraries in Rivers State.

Census sampling was used to select all 41 librarians and 8 system analysts as the study sample. This is (100%) of the population of the study. A structured questionnaire titled "Cybersecurity vulnerability and Library Online Environment Questionnaire" (CVLOE). It was a four-point rating scale: strongly agree (SA-4), agree (3-A), strongly disagree (SD), and disagree (D-1). Face and content validity of the instrument was done by two specialists in test and measurement and evaluation. The instrument's reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.86.

The collected data were analysed using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) in the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. The "r" coefficient of the PPMC was used to answer the research questions, while the p-value was used in testing the null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. Where the p-value is equal to or less than the level of significance ($p \leq 0.05$), the null hypotheses were rejected, but where it is higher than the significance level ($p \geq 0.05$), the null hypotheses were accepted.

Table 3.1: Breakdown of the population distribution of the study.

S/N	University Library	Analysts	Librarians
1	Rivers State University Central Library	2	10
2	Pamo University of Medical Science Library	2	2
3	Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Library	1	9
4	University of Port Harcourt Donald Ekong Library	2	18
5	Madonna University Library	1	2
6	Federal University of Environment and Technology, Saakpewa	1	1

Total	8	41
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Source: Office of the University Librarian of libraries under study (2024/2025)

Results and Discussion

Research question 1: What is the relationship between network security and the safeguarding of the university library's online environment?

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between network security and the safeguarding of the university library's online environment.

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation on the relationship between network security and the safeguarding of university library online environment, University libraries in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Correlation

Variables		Network security	Safeguarding LOE
Network security	Pearson Correlation	1	.669**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	49	49
Safeguarding ULOE	Pearson Correlation	.669**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	49	49

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 presents the summary of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation on the relationship between network security and the safeguarding of the university library's online environment in university libraries in Rivers State, Nigeria. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation coefficient between the two variables is $r = 0.669$, this result indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between the variables.

The hypothesis posits a significant relationship between network security and the safeguarding of the university library's online environment. This is because the p-value is statistically significant at 0.000 and is less than the 0.05 level of significance ($p = .000 < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative accepted.

Research question 2: What is the relationship between system security and the safeguarding of the online environment of university libraries in River State?

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between system security and the safeguarding of the online environment of university libraries in River State.

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation on the relationship between system security and the safeguarding of the online environment of university libraries in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Correlations

Variables	System security	Safeguarding ULO E
system security	Pearson Correlation	.351**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	119
safeguarding ULO E	Pearson Correlation	.351**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	119

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 presents a summary of Pearson product-moment correlations for the relationship between system security and the safeguarding of university library online environments in Rivers State, Nigeria. The result indicates a weak positive relationship between the two variables with a correlation coefficient of ($r=.351$). There is also a significant relationship between system security and the safeguarding of the online environment of university libraries in Rivers State, Nigeria. This is because the p-value is statistically significant at 0.000 and is less than the 0.05 level of significance ($p=.000<0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the reverse is upheld.

Research question 3: What is the relationship between application security and the safeguarding of the university library's online environment?

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between application security and the safeguarding of university library online environment in university libraries in Rivers State

Table 3: Summary of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation on the relationship between application security and the safeguarding of university library online environment in university libraries in Rivers State.

Correlations

Variables	Apps security	Safeguarding ULO E
Apps security	Pearson Correlation	.842**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001
	N	49
Safeguarding ULO E	Pearson Correlation	.842**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001
	N	49

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 shows the summary of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation on the relationship between application security and the safeguarding of university library online environment in university libraries in Rivers State. The result indicates a very strong positive relationship between the two constructs with a correlation coefficient value of ($r=.842$). The result further indicates a significant relationship between application security and the safeguarding of the university library's online environment, as the p-value is less than the significance level ($p = .001 < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the reverse hypothesis upheld.

Discussion of Findings

The findings on network security revealed a strong positive relationship between network security and the safeguarding of the university library's online environment. This outcome suggests that improvements in network security measures, such as firewalls, intrusion detection systems, and secure network configurations, strongly enhance the protection of digital resources and online services in university libraries. This result is consistent with the study of Igbinovia and Ishola (2023), which emphasises that effective network security is foundational to the stability and safety of online library operations, particularly in environments vulnerable to cyber-attacks. It also aligns with the findings of Kon (2024), who asserts that robust network protection plays a critical role in minimising unauthorised access, data breaches, and service interruptions in academic information systems.

Also, the results show a strong but positive relationship between system security and the safeguarding of the online environments of university libraries. Although the correlation strength is lower than in network security, the significance level indicates that the relationship is statistically meaningful, leading to rejection of the null hypothesis. This finding suggests that system-level protections such as operating system updates, antivirus software, authentication controls, and device-level configurations contribute to online environment safety, but not as strongly as network-wide protections. This aligns with studies by Gujar and Pandey (2024), who note that system security measures, though essential, often serve as secondary layers of protection and may be less effective when network-level vulnerabilities persist. It is also in line with Oladokun et al. (2024), who similarly argue that system security contributes to safeguarding digital platforms but requires integration with broader cybersecurity protocols to produce substantial protective outcomes. The implication is that university libraries should strengthen system security but pair it with robust network and application defences to achieve comprehensive online safety. Findings on application security indicate a very strong positive relationship between application security and the safeguarding of the university library's online environment. The high correlation indicates that secure software applications, authentication systems, database protection, and controlled-access platforms significantly enhance the security of online library services. This demonstrates that application security is critical to ensuring the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of digital library resources. This observation is supported by Aregbesola and Nwolise (2023) and Abid (2021), who highlight that application-layer vulnerabilities are among the most frequently exploited entry points for attackers, underscoring the need for secure applications to protect online academic systems. The implication is that universities must invest in strong application security frameworks, regular updates, and secure coding practices to maintain a safe and reliable online environment for users.

Conclusion

The study concludes that cybersecurity is a critical determinant in safeguarding the online environment of university libraries in Rivers State. Network security, system security, and application security each play significant roles, though their impacts differ in magnitude. Application security emerged as the most influential factor, underscoring the importance of secure library software, authentication systems, and protected databases in preventing unauthorised access and cyber threats. Network security also demonstrates a strong effect, highlighting the need for robust network configurations and monitoring, while system security contributes positively but to a lesser extent. Safeguarding the online environment of university libraries could be achieved when the three security components work together.

University libraries and universities should adopt comprehensive cybersecurity measures, including strong application protections, secure network configurations, up-to-date systems and security software,

and ongoing staff training. Establishing and enforcing clear policies on data handling, access control, and password management is essential to safeguarding digital assets and preventing cyber threats..

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